

Impact of Draw Frame Variables on Fibre Orientation and Yarn Quality

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Abstract

The impact of draft/doubling on breaker and finisher draw frame and delivery speed on finisher draw frame on fibre orientation in sliver and cotton yarn quality parameter was investigated by using L9 Orthogonal array experimental design. It was found that draft/doubling on breaker and finisher draw frame and delivery speed of finisher draw frame influences the fibre orientation in sliver. Fibre orientation parameters such as orientation index in sliver observed maximum and sliver U% was minimum with optimum values of draft/doubling and delivery speed of finisher draw frame. Yarn U%, imperfections, hairiness, RKM and elongation were influenced by fibre orientation index. Higher RKM and elongation was observed with even yarn.

Keywords: Draw frame, draft, doubling, orientation index, U%, Imperfections and RKM.

Introduction

In spun yarn manufacturing draw frame is the process used to improve the evenness of sliver and final yarn. The unevenness of the in-process material increases after draw frame process. This is because of two reasons. Firstly, the reduction in number of fibres in the cross section steadily. Uniform arrangement of fibre is difficult with lesser number of fibres. Secondly each drafting operation increases the irregularity in drafted fibre strand. In order to achieve uniform yarn, the process must include operations that give an equalizing effect. These can be doubling, leveling, and drawing [1]. Draw frame sliver has a huge impact on yarn quality parameter like evenness, imperfection, hairiness index, strength and elongation of yarn. The yarn quality parameters are influenced by doubling and drafting parameters of draw frame. Drafting is the reduction in weight per unit length [2]. Fibre mixing is also improved by doubling of slivers at breaker draw frame and finisher draw frame [3]. The doubling and drafting on draw frame reduce long term variations and short-term variations are added [4]. Draw frame process variables and settings influence the fibre arrangement in sliver and it influences on yarn evenness, imperfections and strength [5, 6, 7]. The present paper attempts to study more thoroughly the effect of breaker and finisher draw frame process variables on yarn quality.

Material and Method:

The present study was carried out by using 100% cotton fibre used as raw material for draw frame sliver manufacturing. The average fibre quality parameters were - 2.5% span length- 30.0 mm, bundle strength- 28.50 g/tex, micronair - 3.87 $\mu\text{gm/inch}$, and uniformity ratio- 48.00. The mixing was processed through blow room, card, breaker draw frame and finisher

draw frame. Total nine finisher draw frame sliver samples were produced by using L9 Orthogonal array experimental design with three levels of draft and doubling on breaker and finisher draw frame and three levels of delivery speed on finisher draw frame as given in Table 1. Finisher draw frame sliver samples were processed through speed frame and ring frame to spin 34 Ne yarn count. Lindsley clamped indirect technique was used to measure the fiber orientation in finisher draw frame sliver. Before testing, all the prepared yarn samples were conditioned in the laboratory under standard atmospheric conditions of $27\pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ and a relative humidity of 65 ± 2 for 24 h. Yarn evenness, imperfections and hairiness were determined by using Uster Tester-5 S400. Single yarn strength and elongation% were determined by using Uster Tensorapid -3.

Table 1: L9 Orthogonal array experimental design.

Sample code	Breaker D/F Draft/Doubling	Finisher D/F Draft/Doubling	Finisher D/F Del. Speed (m/min)
S1	6	6	250
S2	6	7	400
S3	6	8	550
S4	7	6	400
S5	7	7	550
S6	7	8	250
S7	8	6	550
S8	8	7	250
S9	8	8	400

Result and Discussion:

The yarn test results for various properties are given in Table 2. The significance of three experimental factors draft/doubling on breaker and finisher draw frame and delivery speed on finisher draw frame on various yarn properties was assessed with the help of ANOVA-general linear model analysis. The confidence level used was 95%.

Table 2: Effect of Draw frame variables on fibre orientation and yarn properties.

Sample No.	Orientation Index		DF-II Sliver U%	Roving U%	Yarn U%	IPI/ Km	Hairiness	RKM	Elongation%
	Leading	Trailing							
S1	0.9564	0.9490	3.71	4.52	13.49	1526	5.21	14.79	3.76
S2	0.9570	0.9490	3.18	3.79	12.96	1542	5.22	14.58	3.93
S3	0.9548	0.9509	3.69	4.61	13.77	1712	5.28	14.21	3.77
S4	0.9447	0.9427	2.89	3.85	13.26	1543	4.93	14.31	3.74
S5	0.9510	0.9376	3.83	4.97	13.73	1550	4.97	14.69	3.81
S6	0.9514	0.9458	3.33	4.23	12.98	1432	4.83	14.66	3.95
S7	0.9480	0.9381	4.29	5.31	13.68	1515	4.97	15.12	3.86
S8	0.9529	0.9514	3.34	4.41	13.33	1504	4.92	14.13	3.68
S9	0.9439	0.9380	4.00	5.04	13.66	1655	4.83	14.11	3.48

Effect of draw frame process variable on fibre orientation index:

Table 2 and Fig. 1 depicts the effect of breaker and finisher draw frame process variables on fiber orientation in finisher draw frame sliver.

Fig. 1: Effect of draw frame process variable on fibre orientation index.

. Increase in DF-I draft/doubling shows decrease in orientation index in leading direction. This may be due to increase in fibre mass and draft the fibre orientation index in leading direction decreases. But with increase in draft/doubling in DF-I initially shows decrease in orientation index and further increase in draft/doubling in DF-I shows marginal increase in orientation index in trailing direction. This may be due to high mass of fibre with 8 doubling the removal of trailing hooks with draft of 8 improves and shows the improvement in the fibre orientation index.

Increase in DF-II draft/doubling initially orientation index increases then decreases in both directions. This is may be because of increase in doubling increases number of fibers in cross section. Due to increase in surrounding fibers the removal of hooks increases and shows increase in orientation index in both the directions. Further increase in draft/doubling to 8 shows decrease in orientation index in both the directions and this may be due to increase in

fibre mass and high draft leading to less control over the moving fibre, which results in decrease in fibre orientation.

Increase in delivery speed from 250 to 400 m/min decrease the orientation index and further increases in delivery speed 400 to 550 m/min shows marginal increase in orientation index in leading direction. Orientation index in trailing direction reduces as delivery speed increases.

Effect of draw frame process variables on finisher draw frame sliver U%:

Table 2 and Fig. 2 shows the effect of breaker and finisher draw frame process variables on finisher draw frame sliver unevenness. The sliver unevenness decreases in DF-I and DF-II as draft/doubling increases from 6 to 7 because of doubling effect, further increase in draft/doubling from 7 to 8 marginally increases the sliver unevenness and is may be because of increase in fiber mass in drafting.

The lower unevenness is observed for 400 mt/min delivery speed in finisher draw frame. As delivery speed increase to 550 mt/min sliver unevenness increases due to fiber movement with higher speed leading less control over moving fibre.

Fig. 2: Effect of draw frame process variables on sliver U%.

Effect of draw frame process variables on yarn U%:

Table 2 and Fig. 3 shows the effect of breaker and finisher draw frame process variables on yarn unevenness. The yarn unevenness decreases as DF-I and DF-II as draft/doubling increases from 6 to 7. This is because of doubling effect the sliver evenness improves and same is transferred in yarn. Further increase in draft/doubling in DF-I and DF-II, from 7 to 8 shows increases in the yarn unevenness and is may be because of increase in fiber mass in drafting results increase in finisher draw frame sliver unevenness and same is transferred in yarn.

Fig. 3: Effect of draw frame process variables on yarn U%.

The increase in DF-II delivery speed shows marginal increase in yarn unevenness initially further increase in delivery speed shows noticeable increase in yarn unevenness. The same trend is observed in DF-II sliver unevenness, and is because of increases in fiber movement with higher drafting speed leading less control over moving fibre.

Effect of draw frame process variables on yarn imperfections:

Table 2 and Fig. 4 shows the effect of breaker and finisher draw frame process variables on yarn imperfections. The increase in DF-I draft/doubling from 6 to 7 shows decrease in yarn imperfections. Further increase in draft/doubling from 7 to 8 shows increase in yarn imperfections. This is because, the yarn unevenness and imperfections always show the same trend. As yarn unevenness increases the imperfections increases and vice-versa.

Fig. 4: Effect of draw frame process variables on yarn imperfections.

The yarn imperfection increases as draft/doubling on DF-II increases. Marginal increase in imperfections is observed as doubling/draft increased from 6 to 7 on DF-II. Further increase in draft/doubling on DF-II shows noticeable increase in imperfections in yarn and this is may be because of excessive feed mass to drafting on DF-II which leads decrease in fibre

orientation in delivered sliver. This decrease in fibre orientation affects the drafting on ring frame and shows increase in imperfections. Increase in delivery speed of DF-II shows increase in imperfections. This is may be due to increase in DF-II delivery speed affects the sliver drafting and increases unopened fibers and clustered fibers in delivered sliver which increases thick and thin places in yarn shows increase in yarn imperfections.

Effect of draw frame process variables on yarn hairiness:

Table 2 and Fig. 5 shows the effect of breaker and finisher draw frame process variables on yarn hairiness. As draft/doubling increases in DF-I from 6 to 7, hairiness drastically reduces. This may be due to the even yarn at the 7 doubling. Further increase in draft/doubling from 7 to 8 shows no change in hairiness.

Increase in draft/doubling in DF-II shows marginal change in yarn hairiness. Increase in DF-II delivery speed increases yarn hairiness and this may be due to decrease in fibre orientation in DF-II sliver and reflecting in an increase in yarn hairiness.

Fig. 5: Effect of draw frame process variables on yarn hairiness.

Effect of draw frame process variables on RKM and elongation of yarn:

Table 2 and Fig. 6 shows the effect of breaker and finisher draw frame process variables on RKM and elongation of yarn. Increase in draft/doubling at DF-I initially shows marginal increase in both RKM and elongation and then shows noticeable decrease. This is because of, with increase in draft/doubling from 6 to 7 on DF-I shows decrease in yarn U% and imperfections and further increase in draft/doubling to 8 on DF-I shows decrease in RKM and elongation of yarn. Even yarn has the higher RKM and elongation than the uneven yarn.

Increase in draft/doubling at DF-II show decrease in RKM of yarn and elongation of yarn initially shows marginal increase and then shows drastic decrease. The same trend is observed in yarn U% and imperfections. Uneven yarn leads to decrease in RKM and elongation of yarn.

Fig. 6: Effect of draw frame process variables on yarn RKM and elongation.

Increase in DF-II delivery speed from 250 to 400 m/min shows decrease in RKM and elongation of yarn. Further increase in delivery speed from 400 to 550 m/min shows decrease in RKM and elongation of yarn. This may be due to initial increase in drafting speed from 250 to 400 m/min decreases the average fibre orientation index and further increase in delivery speed from 400 to 550 m/min increases the average fibre orientation index due to increase in drafting force. The same is transferred in final yarn and shows with better fibre orientation yarn giving higher RKM and elongation and vice-versa.

Conclusion:

Draft/Doubling on breaker and finisher draw frame and delivery speed of finisher draw frame influence the fiber orientation in sliver. Fiber orientation parameters such as orientation index in sliver is maximum and Sliver U% is minimum with optimum values of draft/doubling and delivery speed of finisher draw frame. Yarn U%, imperfections, hairiness, RKM and elongation are influenced by fiber orientation index. Even yarn has higher RKM and elongation.

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